

Light Time Travel Effect in KU Aur and DK Her Eclipsing Binaries

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Abstract. This paper discusses the variations in the orbital periods of two eclipsing binaries (KU Aur and DK Her). The potential effects on the period of light due to the presence of third bodies in these systems have been the subject of further investigation. We have calculated a mass function and an orbital period of $0.00818 \pm 0.00002 M_{\odot}$, 26.85 ± 1.23 years and $0.25862 \pm 0.00168 M_{\odot}$, 123.79 ± 4.72 years for the theoretical third bodies of KU Aur and DK Her, respectively.

Keywords: binaries, eclipsing, light- time-travel effect, stars: individual: KU Aur and DK Her

INTRODUCTION

Eclipsing binaries are excellent objects for studying the physical properties of stars. They can also be used to detect additional companions in target binary systems. The elliptical or circular motion of a binary star around the mass-centre of a triple system with an eclipsing binary star and a third body will cause apparent changes in its orbital period. This is called the Light-Time-Travel Effect (LTT Effect). Irwin (1959) modified the method described by Woltjer (1922) for analysing the long term change of the minimum times of target binaries due to the LTT effect of a third body. Here, the LTT effects in KU Aur and DK Her binaries, have been studied using the O-C analysis programme written by Zasche (2009) based on the Irwin method.

OBSERVATION

The eccentric binary stars KU Aur was observed photometrically at the TESS. This photometric observation was carried out in the V filter. The new minimum times and their standard errors were performed using the method of Kwee and van Woerden (1956) and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. New minimum times of KU Aur

System	BJD+2400000	Error	Type	Filter	Observatory
KU Aur	58843.3126	0.0008	I	V	TESS
	58844.6320	0.0008	I	V	TESS
	58845.9515	0.0007	I	V	TESS
	58847.2708	0.0008	I	V	TESS
	58848.5906	0.0008	I	V	TESS
	58849.9102	0.0007	I	V	TESS
	58851.2299	0.0007	I	V	TESS
	58852.5494	0.0008	I	V	TESS
	58853.8689	0.0007	I	V	TESS

58856.4540	0.0001	I	V	TESS
58857.8276	0.0007	I	V	TESS
58859.1472	0.0007	I	V	TESS
58860.4669	0.0008	I	V	TESS
58861.7864	0.0007	I	V	TESS
58863.1061	0.0007	I	V	TESS
58864.4257	0.0008	I	V	TESS
58865.7452	0.0007	I	V	TESS
58867.0645	0.0008	I	V	TESS
58868.3844	0.0008	I	V	TESS
58842.6543	0.0046	II	V	TESS
58843.9742	0.0043	II	V	TESS
58845.2940	0.0041	II	V	TESS
58846.6134	0.0047	II	V	TESS
58847.9322	0.0046	II	V	TESS
58849.2526	0.0049	II	V	TESS
58850.5723	0.0046	II	V	TESS
58851.8919	0.0044	II	V	TESS
58853.2106	0.0053	II	V	TESS
58854.5302	0.0045	II	V	TESS
58858.4893	0.0044	II	V	TESS
58859.8090	0.0042	II	V	TESS
58861.1281	0.0049	II	V	TESS
58862.4481	0.0044	II	V	TESS
58863.7680	0.0041	II	V	TESS
58865.0874	0.0049	II	V	TESS
58866.4066	0.0042	II	V	TESS
58867.7267	0.0041	II	V	TESS

ANALYSIS OF INDIVIDUAL SYSTEMS

KU AUR

The other names and fundamental informations of KU Aur eclipsing binary is TYC 2422-20-1, 2MASS J06280439+3023338, TIC 171853918, ATO J097.0183+30.3928, V* KU Aur, SV* SON 5424, WISEA J062804.40+302333.9UCAC2 42390080, GSC 02422-00020, SV* WR 99, WISE J062804.40+302333.9, UCAC4 602-032925, $\alpha_{2000} = 06^{\text{h}} 28^{\text{m}} 04^{\text{s}}.39$, $\delta_{2000} = 30^{\circ} 23' 33''.771$, $V_{\text{max}} = 11^{\text{m}}.72$, spectral type = F8 and $P = 1.319579$ days. It was discovered by Popowa (1961). The light curve of this system was analyzed by Lacy (2004). Later, its spectral type was given as F8 by Luo et al. (2015). In the atlas of O-C diagrams published by Kreiner (2004), it is clear from the figure that the orbital period of this system varies. Linear light elements were given by Kreiner (2004). The O - C period analysis was first performed by Zasche et al. (2020). The following linear light elements were used to compute O-C values of the system:

$$\text{Min I} = \text{HJD } 2429631.129 + 1.319579 \times E \quad (1)$$

A total of 96 times of minima of KU Aur was used for analysing period variation in the system. Zasche (2009)'s program was applied to these O-C values. The O-C diagrams of KU Aur are presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2, and the resulting parameters are given in Table 2.

FIGURE 1. The O-C diagram of KU Aur

FIGURE 2. Sinusoidal fit on the O-C diagram of KU Aur

TABLE 2. Parameters derived from O-C analysis of KU Aur in this study.

Parametre	KU Aur
T_0 (HJD)	2429631.1219 ± 0.0044
P_{orb} (day)	1.3195794 ± 0.0000007
Q (day)	$(-0.1175 \pm 0.0003) \cdot 10^{-10}$
a_{12sini_3} (AB)	1.8063 ± 0.3069
A_s (day)	0.0102 ± 0.0017
e'	0.2412 ± 0.0017
ω' (deg)	323.46 ± 5.95
T_3 (HJD)	2455382.573 ± 158.244
P_3 (yr)	26.84 ± 1.23
$f(M_3)$ (M_\odot)	0.008177 ± 0.000018
(M_3) (M_\odot)	0.35
$i = 90$	

$(M_3) (M_\odot)$	0.41
$i = 60$	
$(M_3) (M_\odot)$	0.80
$i = 30$	

DK HER

The eclipsing binary is DK Her (HD 155700, GSC 00989-00891, TYC 989-891-1, Gaia DR3 4541653041911060992, AN 16.1930, 2MASS J17124395+1311038, V* DK Her, Gaia DR1 4541653037613187456, CSI+13-17104, TIC 154641035, Gaia DR2 4541653041911060992, $\alpha_{2000} = 17^h 12^m 43^s.95$, $\delta_{2000} = 13^\circ 11' 03''.76$, $V_{\max} = 10^m.87$, spectral type = A1 ve $P = 1.942293$ days). It was discovered by Panaitescu and Kumar (2004). In the atlas of O-C diagrams published by Kreiner (2004) it is clear from the figure that the orbital period of this system varies. Linear light elements were given by Kreiner (2004). Later, the spectral type of DK Her was presented as A1IV by Luo et al. (2015). The light curve analysis and O - C period analysis was first performed by Zasche et al. (2020). A total of 31 minimum times of DK Her were used for the period changing analysis of the target systems. The linear ephemerides were used to calculate the O - C values

$$\text{Min I} = \text{HJD } 2425730.445 + 1.942293 \times E \quad (2)$$

The programme of Zasche (2009) was used with these O - C values. The O - C diagrams of the target system are given in Figure 3 and Figure 4 and the result obtained parameters are also reported in Table 3.

TABLE 3. O-C changing diagram of DK Her.

TABLE 4. Sinusoidal fit on the O-C changing diagram of DK Her.

TABLE 3. In this study, the parameters were derived from the O-C analysis of DK Her.

Parametre	DK Her
T_0 (HJD)	2425730.5199 ± 0.0472
P_{orb} (day)	1.9422834 ± 0.0000265
Q (day)	$(5.142 \pm 0.015) \cdot 10^{-10}$
a_{12sini_3} (AB)	16.61 ± 0.71
A_s (day)	0.0959 ± 0.0098
e'	0.0079 ± 0.0038
ω' (deg)	51.7 ± 7.4
T_3 (HJD)	24516891.742 ± 88.911
P_3 (yr)	123.4 ± 4.9
$f(M_3)$ (M_\odot)	0.3014 ± 0.0026
(M_3) (M_\odot)	1.56
$i = 90$	
(M_3) (M_\odot)	1.92
$i = 60$	
(M_3) (M_\odot)	4.82
$i = 30$	

CONCLUSION

In this study we present the reanalysis of the changes in the orbital periods of two W UMa type eclipsing binaries, O - C changing diagrams created from all minimum times. According to the obtained results, the LTT effect due to a third companion in target binary systems could explain the apparent changes in the orbital periods of two binary systems. The mass function was determined to be $0.00818 \pm 0.00002 M_\odot$ and $0.25862 \pm 0.00168 M_\odot$ for the assumed third body of KU Aur and DK Her respectively. The orbital periods of the third bodies were also determined as 26.85 ± 1.23 and 123.79 ± 4.72 years for KU Aur and DK Her, respectively.

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